

IMPORTANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: The article discusses the new types of pedagogical methods in teaching English and the methods of its application in the classroom, as well as the practical importance of the effective use of methods. Therefore, it is noted that these methods are useful for students to master another language and speak it fluently.

Keywords: method, English, effective, education, student, foreign language ICT.

INTRODUCTION

It's clear that from the meeting of the video selector dedicated to the improvement of the foreign language teaching system chaired by our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev, it was emphasized that from 2021 foreign language teachers will be required to have national and international certificates. This is a responsible job for us foreign language teachers. Now, instead of traditional teaching methods, we should organize the teaching process based on interactive methods using new ICT. This training is also a requirement of the times, and the teacher has to work even more on himself. While paying attention to new methods of teaching in the article, first of all, it is necessary to take consideration to the type and effectiveness of these methods.

It should be noted that new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of foreign language teachers' knowledge and skills. According to it, textbooks are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening comprehension and speaking), and specific concepts and skills are given for each of them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, shows, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method;
- CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

In the course of foreign language lessons, it is necessary to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Advanced methods serve as a compound in the thorough mastery of a foreign language.

One such method is the use of role-playing games in the teaching process. Role-playing games are the application of different situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This method helps to create a language environment during the lesson.

For example, Case 1: old friends meet by chance. Case 2: A child who does not follow the rules of the road while crossing the road, that is, crosses the road where there is no crossing. Case 3. A customer enters the store to buy food. Case 4: Scenes are played out for these situations. Such life-like role-playing games create a language environment in the course of the lesson, and give students the opportunity to freely express their thoughts. In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to express their emotional states freely in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role-playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes. Making a mistake and correcting it also helps to learn the language and teaches students about correct pronunciation. The use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson ensures that all students are actively involved in the lesson at the same time. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign language and create a lively, fun atmosphere for the learning process. This serves to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons.

The next method is "Case-study" in English ("case" - specific situation, event, "study" - to study, analyze) is a method aimed at carrying out teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations.

One of the most interesting methods - in the game "Pantomime" is divided into 3 groups. One person from each group is put on the board. They are given different words based on the list. They have to explain the words to the rest of the group through gestures and actions without saying a word.

To apply this method "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read, and how it ends is referred to the judgment of the students; - "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and come up with the answer to a riddle; - "Quick answers" help to improve the effectiveness of the lesson; - "Warm-up exercises" using various games in the classroom to make students interested in the lesson [3]; - "Pantomime" this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or by doing written exercises when the students are tired; - "A chain story" method helps to develop oral speech of students; - "Acting characters" this method can be added in all types of lessons.

In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with the students; - "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the words of wisdom they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people; - "Picture voice" method is very convenient and helps in teaching English and developing the oral speech of students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic; - "Quiz cards" cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time. As we have seen, each

innovative technology has its own advantages. All such methods include cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

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